

SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION SUPPORT AND PHONICS INSTRUCTION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHONEMIC SKILLS OF KINDERGARTEN LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study was to determine the implication of school administration support to kindergarten pupils to develop the phonemic awareness of kindergarten pupils in Deped Tiaong District. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions; What is the extent of school administration support for development of phonemic skills of kindergarten learners in terms of Goal setting for pupil, Academic achievement of pupil, School resource, Funds for school libraries and partnership with parents and community? What is the mean perception of the respondents on phonics instruction in developing pupils' phonemic skills in terms of Extrinsic instruction and Intrinsic instruction? What is the level of kindergarten pupils' phonemic skill in terms of Sounding of words, Blending of sound, Reading syllables and reading word with CVC pattern and Is the level of kindergarten pupils' phonemic skills significantly related to Administrative support and Phonics instruction for kindergarten pupils. This study employed descriptive survey method. The respondents of the study were 48 kindergarten teachers in Tiaong District Division of Quezon In School Year 2020-2021. The researcher -made survey questionnaire was the main instrument used in gathering the data such as the kindergarten teacher's personal information, teacher-respondent perception on the administration support in phonemic skills development of kindergarten pupils. Questionnaires were distributed to 28 schools in Tiaong District collected, tabulate and subjected to statistical tool. It was then analyzed and interpreted using different statistical tools. The salient findings of the study are summarized as follows: all of the kindergarten teacher- respondents in Tiaong District are female described in terms of age, gender, civil status, plantilla position, number of years in teaching, educational, and Early Childhood Education(ECE) units earned. The data gathered in terms of administration support when it comes in goal setting for pupils, academic achievement of pupils, school resources , funds for school libraries and partnership with parents and community revealed that the perception of the respondents is interpreted to a high extend. Based on the perception of the respondents the administration support given in terms of phonics instruction which are extrinsic instruction and intrinsic instruction is on high extent same as phonemic skills of kindergarten pupils the administration support is on high extent also. Results of data analysis revealed that the school administration support of Tiaong District showed strong support to develop phonemic skills of kindergarten pupils. Statistical analysis showed there is significant and strong relationship between the independent variable, the school administration support and the dependent variable, the phonemic skills of Kindergarten pupils which means that multicollinearity exists between them. After several statistical treatments, the data showed that there is a high correlation between the administration support and the development of phonemic skills of kindergarten pupils at Tiaong District in the Division of Quezon.

Keywords: School Administration Support for the Development of Phonemic Skills